

**THE INFLUENCE OF OXIDATION PROCESSES ON THE FUNCTIONAL
ACTIVITY OF INNATIONAL IMMUNITY INDICATORS**

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Many scientific studies carried out in recent years have shown that immunity indicators, including innate immunity indicators, have strong variability at the individual and population level, that is, the range of variation is high, and for different regions the development of normative indicators describes these indicators, in generalized cases such indicators are called normoimmunograms. Research is being carried out on oxygen free radicals, lipid peroxidation caused by disturbances in lipid metabolism, which affect immunity indicators and natural immunity indicators in various pathological conditions [1]. In various literature, the formation of active forms of oxygen as a result of lipid peroxidation and their negative effect on cell membrane lipids, nucleic acids and proteins, as a result of which the loss of enzyme activity, decrease in membrane permeability develops [3], these processes affect the immune system. can cause a decrease in the activity of cells and decrease in quantity. Protects the homeostasis of functional systems with the help of enzymes of the antioxidant system in the body against peroxidation of lipids and is of great importance in the elimination of active forms of oxygen. Together, LPO/AOT participates in the control of the function of various functional systems in the body, such as cell division, phagocytosis, the synthesis of certain hormones depends on these processes, and controls the energy exchange of these processes.

Oxidation-reduction reactions in cells are involved in the homeostasis, activation of T-cells in the immune system, secretion of lymphokines by macrophages, as well as in programmed cell death as a controlling factor in the process of apoptosis [4,5]. Many types of cells in the body, especially T-cells and natural immune cell factors, macrophages, are sensitive to reactive forms of oxygen. When oxidative stress occurs in the body, the process of apoptosis increases, which can be caused by lymphokine and tumor necrosis factor (TNF) synthesized by macrophages and T-cells. When the AOT enzyme superoxide dismutase deficiency occurs, T cells become more sensitive to TNF, ionizing radiation, and hyperthermia [3].

In this regard, studying the existence of connections between AOT parameters and the body's innate immune indicators, on the one hand, can reveal connections that explain the participation of oxidation processes in the immune system, the obtained results are of theoretical and practical importance in this respect the causes of pathological conditions, and on the other hand, the obtained results can be effectively used for diagnostic and research purposes.

Taking into account the important role of free radical oxidation in innate immune processes, it is important to determine the presence of parallel connections between innate immunity indicators and indicators of the intensity of lipid peroxide oxidation processes and the activity of enzymes of the antiradical defense system [2]. As a result of the conducted research, it was found that the amount of MDA was 2.4 ± 0.01 nmol/ml, the activity of CT and SOD was 16.5 ± 0.3 μ kat/l and 1.4 ± 0.04 sh. units/ml. Comparative analysis of the indicators of the LPO-AOT system in age-related groups with different work activities in the population living in Samarkand city and Toyloq district. showed that he did not have it.

However, the obtained data show that the activity of AOT-SOD superoxide dismutase enzyme is higher in conditions of different work activities (in the group of workers working in the production enterprise and in the group of workers working in vegetable farms). the indicator has its own characteristics. In the group of workers operating in vegetable farms, this indicator was lower and more reliable than in the group of workers operating in manufacturing enterprises.

Taking into account the role of organism oxidative stress processes in the homeostasis of innate immunity parameters, an analysis was conducted to determine statistical correlations between the intensity of LPO-AOT reactions and innate immunity parameters. Let's show the innate immunity in the group of people examined by MDA indicators

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